

Theories and Principles of Medical Ethics: An Overview.

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ABSTRACT

Clinical ethics entails the application of ethical theories, principles, rules, and guidelines to clinical situations in medicine. The practice of clinical medicine involves continuous intelligent and thoughtful application of general principles and concepts of clinical ethics to unique clinical circumstances. Therefore, it is important for clinicians to have a basic grounding in ethical theories and principles and to develop the skill of applying these to challenging clinical cases. One common approach to ethics is to begin with ethical theories from which we derive ethical principles, which in turn lead to rules (such as truth-telling or maintaining confidentiality), which then guide and determine our particular judgments and actions. Several general theories of ethical analysis have been proposed. The three most widely employed are consequentialism, deontology, and virtue ethics. Beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, and justice constitute the four principles of ethics. Medical ethics is thus the effort to determine what clinicians should do in complex clinical and research situations. This overview attempts to cover the basics of medical ethics from a perspective of ethical theories and principles. When situations arise in which what should be done is not immediately self-evident, a thorough understanding and application of these theories and principles becomes indispensable and central in ethical analysis to arrive at a correct action.

Keywords: Medical ethics, clinical ethics.

INTRODUCTION

Ethics is an inherent and inseparable part of clinical medicine.¹ Clinical ethics is the application of ethical theories, principles, rules, and guidelines to clinical situations in medicine. Clinical ethics is analogous to clinical medicine because general principles and concepts must be applied intelligently and thoughtfully to unique clinical circumstances.

Thus, it is important for clinicians to have a basic grounding in the ethical theories and principles and to develop a method for applying these to challenging clinical cases. The purpose of ethical analysis is to provide both a perspective from which to judge whether a past action was or was not ethical and a framework from which to determine which of one or more possible future actions would be ethical.²

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One common approach to ethics is to begin with ethical theories from which we derive ethical principles, which in turn lead to rules (such as truth-telling or maintaining confidentiality), which then guide and determine our particular judgments and actions. Several general theories of ethical analysis have been proposed. The three most widely employed are **consequentialism, deontology, and virtue ethics**. These three approaches are often referred to as normative ethics, and attempts to answer the question, “Which general moral norms for the guidance and evaluation of conduct should we accept, and why?”^{2,3}

Beneficence, nonmaleficence, autonomy, and justice constitute the four principles of ethics. The first two can be traced back to the time of Hippocrates “to help and do no harm,” while the latter two evolved later.³

A number of deplorable abuses of human subjects in research, medical interventions without informed consent, experimentation in concentration camps in World War II, along with salutary advances in medicine and medical technology and societal changes, led to the rapid evolution of medical ethics from one concerned about professional conduct and codes to its present status with an extensive scope that includes research ethics, public health ethics, organizational ethics, and clinical ethics.⁴

Ethical Theories

Consequentialism is a system of ethical analysis, most closely associated with John Stuart Mill, that bases the correctness of one's actions on the consequences of the action.⁵ Hence, simplistically, if an action produces good effects, it is ethical, whereas if an action produces evil or bad effects, it is unethical. However, there are several problems with this simplistic analysis, as it may be unclear (or open to interpretation) which effects are good and which are bad.²

Deontology (whereby to be ethical is to do one's duty) is a system of ethical analysis, most closely associated with Immanuel Kant, that bases the correctness of one's actions on fulfilling the duties of the actor.⁶ Thus individuals have moral obligations to others and, if they fulfill those obligations, they are acting ethically; if they

do not, they are acting unethically. Among the major challenges of deontology is to determine the basis of one's duties and the nature of one's duties.

Virtue ethics, whereby ethics is a matter of cultivating appropriate virtues. Another approach to ethics, most closely associated with Aristotle and, more recently MacIntyre (1981)⁷ and Pellegrino (1993)⁸, is to focus on the qualities of the moral agent, or actor, rather than the agent's acts.⁹ In this approach, to be ethical is to cultivate in oneself appropriate character traits, such as honesty, altruism, courage, and perseverance, and also to work to cultivate such character traits in others. According to this approach, if we are perfectly virtuous, we will necessarily do the right thing. Of course, no one can ever be perfectly virtuous so, to the extent we are imperfect, we will require judgment and humility when determining how best to act. Thus virtue ethics emphasizes not only cultivating virtues, but also self-knowledge, especially understanding the limitations of human beings in general and ourselves in particular.

In the real world of medicine, most people find that all three perspectives offer useful insights and are complementary rather than contradictory.

Ethical Principles

The most common approach to clinical ethical analysis is principlism. According to principlism, the medical practitioner must attempt to uphold four important principles: **beneficence, nonmaleficence, respect for patient autonomy and justice**. When these principles conflict, resolving them depends on the details of the case. Alternative approaches to medical ethics, including the primacy of beneficence, care-based ethics, feminist ethics, and narrative ethics, help to define the limitations of principlism and provide a broader perspective on medical ethics.⁴

Beneficence

The principle of beneficence is the obligation of physician to act for the benefit of the patient and supports a number of moral rules to protect and defend the right of others, prevent harm, remove conditions that will cause harm, help persons with disabilities, and rescue persons in danger. It is worth emphasizing that, in distinction to

nonmaleficence, the language here is one of positive requirements. The principle calls for not just avoiding harm, but also to benefit patients and to promote their welfare. While physicians' beneficence conforms to moral rules, and is altruistic, it is also true that in many instances it can be considered a payback for the debt to society for education (often subsidized by governments), ranks and privileges, and to the patients themselves (learning and research).⁴

NON MALEFICENCE

Nonmaleficence is the obligation of a physician not to harm the patient. This simply stated principle supports several moral rules – do not kill, do not cause pain or suffering, do not incapacitate, do not cause offense, and do not deprive others of the goods of life. The practical application of nonmaleficence is for the physician to weigh the benefits against burdens of all interventions and treatments, to eschew those that are inappropriately burdensome, and to choose the best course of action for the patient. This is particularly important and pertinent in difficult end-of-life care decisions on withholding and withdrawing life-sustaining treatment, medically administered nutrition and hydration, and in pain and other symptom control. A physician's obligation and intention to relieve the suffering (e.g., refractory pain or dyspnea) of a patient by the use of appropriate drugs including opioids override the foreseen but unintended harmful effects or outcome (doctrine of double effect).^{10,11}

AUTONOMY

The philosophical underpinning for autonomy, as interpreted by philosophers Immanuel Kant (1724–1804) and John Stuart Mill (1806–1873), and accepted as an ethical principle, is that all persons have intrinsic and unconditional worth, and therefore, should have the power to make rational decisions and moral choices, and each should be allowed to exercise his or her capacity for self-determination.¹² This ethical principle was affirmed in a court decision by Justice Cardozo in 1914 with the epigrammatic dictum, “Every human being of adult years and sound mind has a right to determine what shall be done with his own body”.¹³

Respecting the **principle of autonomy** obliges the physician to disclose medical information and treatment options that are necessary for the patient to exercise self-determination and supports **informed consent, truth-telling, and confidentiality**.

The requirements of an **informed consent** for a medical or surgical procedure, or for research, are that the patient or subject (i) must be competent to understand and decide, (ii) receives a full disclosure, (iii) comprehends the disclosure, (iv) acts voluntarily, and (v) consents to the proposed action.⁴

Truth-telling is a vital component in a physician-patient relationship; without this component, the physician loses the trust of the patient. An autonomous patient has not only the right to know (disclosure) of his/her diagnosis and prognosis, but also has the option to forgo this disclosure. However, the physician must know which of these two options the patient prefers.⁴

Confidentiality: Physicians are obligated not to disclose confidential information given by a patient to another party without the patient's authorization. An obvious exception (with implied patient authorization) is the sharing necessary of medical information for the care of the patient from the primary physician to consultants and other health-care teams. In the present-day modern hospitals with multiple points of tests and consultants, and the use of electronic medical records, there has been an erosion of confidentiality. However, individual physicians must exercise discipline in not discussing patient specifics with their family members or in social gatherings¹⁴ and social media. There are some noteworthy exceptions to patient confidentiality. These include, among others, legally required reporting of gunshot wounds and sexually transmitted diseases and exceptional situations that may cause major harm to another (e.g., epidemics of infectious diseases, partner notification in HIV disease, relative notification of certain genetic risks, etc.).⁴

JUSTICE

Justice is generally interpreted as fair, equitable, and appropriate treatment of persons. Of the several categories of justice, the one that is most pertinent to

clinical ethics is distributive justice. Distributive justice refers to the fair, equitable, and appropriate distribution of health-care resources determined by justified norms that structure the terms of social cooperation.¹⁵ How can this be accomplished? There are different valid principles of distributive justice. These are distribution to each person (i) an equal share, (ii) according to need, (iii) according to effort, (iv) according to contribution, (v) according to merit, and (vi) according to free-market exchanges. Each principle is not exclusive, and can be, and are often combined in application. It is easy to see the difficulty in choosing, balancing, and refining these principles to form a coherent and workable solution to distribute medical resources.

CONCLUSION

Medical ethics is the effort to determine what clinicians should do in complex clinical and research situations.² This overview has attempted to cover the basics of medical ethics from a perspective of ethical theories and principles. When situations arise in which what should be done is not immediately self-evident, a thorough understanding and application of these theories and principles becomes indispensable and central in ethical analysis to arrive at a correct action.

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